

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and
virtual-physical interactions

5 December - Hong Kong

8/9 December – Seattle

13 December - Brussels

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and virtual-physical interactions

#dataforpolicy2022

Hong Kong Programme

5th December, Hong Kong time

Hybrid – In-person and online (Institute for Advanced Study Lecture Theater and Zoom)

*denotes presenting author

†denotes virtual presentation

Schedule

09:00-09:30 Registration

09:30-09:50 Opening Remarks

- Naubahar **Sharif**, Professor and Acting Head, Division of Public Policy, HKUST
- Masaru **Yarime**, Asia-Pacific Regional Chair, Data for Policy 2022, HKUST

09:50-10:40 Keynote Speech

Chair: Masaru Yarime

- “Data-driven Society: Toward the Democratization of Innovation,” Noboru **Koshizuka**†, Professor, Graduate School of Interdisciplinary Information Studies (GSII), The University of Tokyo, Japan

10:40-11:15 Session “Data, Emerging Technologies and Citizens”

Chairs: Eleonore **Fournier-Tombs** (United Nations University Institute in Macau)

- [2186] Elizaveta **Dorrer*** and Masaru **Yarime** (Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “Normalisation of facial recognition technologies: Interplay of top-down enforcement by the government and internalisation by the public – Case study of Moscow Metro”
- [2232] Yifan **Liu***, M. Cade **Lawson** (Georgia Institute of Technology), Catharina **Hollauer** (Ludwig Maximilian University) and Omar I. **Asensio** (Georgia Institute of Technology). “Citizen Generated Intelligence for Transport Electrification Policies”
- [9288] Veronica Qin Ting **Li***, Carla-Leanne **Washbourne** and Yasminah **Beebeejaun** (University College London). “Social media data for inclusive and salient energy policies in the United Kingdom”

11:15-11:35 Break

11:35-12:10 Session “Government Policy and Regulation on Data-Driven Innovations”

Chair: Kira **Matus** (Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

- [929] Kris **Hartley***† (City University of Hong Kong). “Measuring the political perceptions of smart city programs: public awareness and government communication in Hong Kong”
- [4076] Jing **Wu***† (University of Tokyo). Performance of E-government in China during the COVID-19 period.
- [3718] Gleb **Papyshev*** and Masaru **Yarime** (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “The Brussels Effect of Artificial Intelligence: A Comparative Analysis of AI Regulation in the EU and Russia”

12:10-12:25 Demonstration

- Natalia **Grincheva***† (LASALLE College of the Arts, The University of Melbourne). “Data intense research and computation tools for cultural diplomacy”

12:25-13:40 Lunch

13:40-14:30 Plenary “Facilitating Data-driven Innovations: Opportunities and Challenges”

Chair: Masaru **Yarime** (Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

- Kira **Matus** (Professor, Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)
- Junseok **Hwang** (Professor, Technology Management, Economics and Policy Program (TEMEP), Seoul National University, South Korea)
- Sabrina **Luk** (Nanyang Technological University, Singapore)

14:30-15:15 Session “Political Economy of Data Policies and Strategies”

Chair: Mushan **Jin** (Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

- [6550] Ian Varela **Soares***, Masaru **Yarime**, and Magdalena **Klemun** (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “Balancing the Trade-off between Data Center Development and Its Environmental Impacts: A Comparative Analysis of Policymaking in Singapore and Amsterdam”

- [7705] Timothy Joseph **Henares*** (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “The political economy of China’s Digital Silk Road: A case study on New Clark City, Philippines”
- [4158] Debora Valentina **Malito*†** (Xi’an Jiaotong-Liverpool University), Gaby **Umbach** (European University Institute) and Antonio **Savoia** (University of Manchester). “Developing Data for Policy: Mapping the Political Economy of Measuring Governance”
- [8950] Wilson **Wong** (The Chinese University of Hong Kong), Kelvin **Lo** (The Chinese University of Hong Kong) and Tony **Wong*** (The Chinese University of Hong Kong). “Data for Social Equity in the AI Era? A Global Perspective of National Strategies and Challenges of Transformation”

15:15-15:35 Break

15:35-16:20 Session “Governance and Management of Data-driven Innovations”

Chair: Tony **Wong** (Chinese University of Hong Kong)

- [1228] Atsushi **Koyama†** and So **Morikawa†** (University of Tokyo). “Governance rules for logistics service providers in the era of the Physical Internet”
- [2958] Siqi **Xie*** (Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (Guangzhou)) and Masaru **Yarime** (Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “Are Digital Innovation Policies Effective in Promoting the Development of Digital Economy in China?”
- [8471] Joni **Jupesta*†**, Keigo **Akimoto** (Research Institute of Innovative Technology for the Earth (RITE)) and Bayu Dwi Apri **Nugroho** (University of Gajah Mada). “Green Supply Chain towards Industry 5.0”
- [7302] Xiaohui **Jiang*** and Masaru **Yarime** (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology). “The Smart City as a Field of Innovation: Effects of Public-Private Data Collaboration on the Innovative Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in China”

16:20-17:10 Plenary “Data-driven Innovations to Tackle Societal Challenges”

Chair: Masaru **Yarime** (Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

- Wanxin **Li**, Associate Professor, School of Energy and Environment, City University of Hong Kong, and Visiting Associate Professor, Tsinghua University, China.
- P. Vigneswara **Ilavarasan†**, Professor, School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi, India.

17:10-17:30 Closing Remarks

Masaru **Yarime** (Division of Public Policy, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

17:30-18:30 Reception and networking

With thanks to our partner organisations
